

BASIC VERIFICATION METHODS

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Abstract: In this article, we examined the main verification methods

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The main methods of examination of a dental patient include:

- interviewing the patient;
- examination of the patient;
- palpation of the soft tissues of the face and mouth;
- probing;
- percussion.

relatives and close people, as well as medical documentation related to the patient (objective medical history).

The data obtained are presented in the form of three sections:

- 1) patient's complaints;
- 2) anamnesis of life;
- 3) anamnesis of the present disease.

the actors are active. In some cases, patients for one reason or another do not report very important manifestations of the disease, they should be detected accurately using objective medical history data. The time when the first signs of the present disease appeared, the nature of their occurrence and further course are being clarified. It is important to find out the circumstances under which the disease began, and possible etiological factors.

In addition to identifying complaints indicating signs of the disease, questioning the patient allows you to assess the course of the disease and the treatment being carried out. Usually the doctor asks what is bothering the patient, directs the patient's story with leading questions. During the survey, it is necessary to ask about the first manifestations of the disease, about the dynamics of its development, what worries the patient at this point in time, whether treatment was carried out earlier and what are the results of the treatment. The general well-being of the patient, the condition of other organs and systems, complaints about changes in their activities, and the limitation period of common diseases are also being clarified. Clarification of this information makes it possible to establish a causal relationship with changes in the oral cavity.

Due to the significant increase in the number of diseases based on hypersensitivity to drugs, products or household items, it is necessary to clarify the allergological history during the analysis. The survey establishes not only the medical history of the disease, but also the living and working conditions. Everyday professional factors can contribute to increased abrasion of dental tissues (acid vapors), an increase in dental caries (carbohydrates when working at a confectionery factory). Harmful habits that favor damage to the organs of the oral cavity (smoking) are being clarified. An important role in the diagnosis is played by a painful symptom, which most often causes the patient to consult a doctor. The famous Russian doctor T.A. Zakharin considered the patient's survey an art. He wrote: "No matter how much you listen to the patient and tap, you will never be able to accurately identify the disease if you do not listen to the testimony of the patient himself, if you do not learn, if you do not learn another art to explore the mental state of the patient."

It is necessary to find out the causes and time of pain (night attacks are characteristic of pulpitis; absence of pain at night and the presence of pain when pressing trigger zones). Of great importance in making a diagnosis is the definition of localization, the nature of pain (aching, twitching, pulsating), duration (paroxysmal, constant), concentration of pain (localized or generalized). Pain can occur under the influence of external stimuli (thermal, mechanical, chemical), as well as without the influence of these stimuli. A detailed study of the pain symptom allows the doctor to determine the initial data of the disease when making a diagnosis.

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